

Statistical Context of Semiclassical Quantum Variance and Entropy

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Classical mechanics is deterministic in that it links x and t i.e. $x(t)$ from which one may take derivatives to obtain velocity and acceleration. We argued in (1) that quantum mechanics is a statistical theory which represents the decoupling of x and t . If this is the case, what does it mean to say that large n approaches classical mechanics (correspondence principle) or to use semiclassical approaches such as $\int p dx = n\hbar$ where the integral is between the classical turning points? We consider this question and also try to apply the semiclassical approaches of (2) to the calculation of the variance of p and x . In particular we consider a particle in a box with infinite potential walls and an oscillator. We also consider $S_p = - \int a(p)a(p) \ln[a(p)a(p)]$ where $W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and try to argue that this quantity may not have a semiclassical analogue while $S_x = - \int dx W(x)W(x) \ln[W(x)W(x)]$ does. In other words there may be a spatial correspondence principle, but not a momentum one with respect to Shannon's entropy.

Quantum Mechanics as a Statistical Theory Versus Classical Mechanics as a Deterministic One

Classical mechanics is deterministic in the sense that x and t are coupled to give $x(t)$ from which time derivatives yield velocity and acceleration. In (1) we argued that quantum mechanics is a statistical theory which decouples x and t . As a result, a bound state wavefunction consists of a distribution of $\exp(ipx)$'s with no time present i.e. $W(x)=\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. Time appears only in the factor $\exp(-iEt)$ which describes the overall resonance. As a result, forward and backwards motion which would be separated in time in classical mechanics are considered together.

If classical mechanics is deterministic and quantum mechanics is statistical, how does one still have a statistical picture for large n if this is supposed to match classical mechanics? Consider an ensemble of quantum single particle states in boxes with infinite potential walls all at a very high n in a room. The systems are one dimensional, all centered at $x=0$, but there is no information about time within the systems even though there is a clock in the room. Though a classical mechanical treatment of each box would be deterministic, the situation above is a statistical one. On average if one performed measurements one would expect half of the momenta to be $+p_{\text{ave}}$ and the other half $-p_{\text{ave}}$. The average momentum is 0 and so there is a p variance. From the point of view of classical mechanics of a single deterministic system this is unusual because p variance measures the deviation from the average. If one follows a particle along it has one velocity and there are no deviations from it, hence no concept of variance. It is only if one takes the ensemble approach and decouples space and time that one sees a large n statistical scenario. Thus we argue one must be careful about linking large n quantum mechanics to classical mechanics.

To demonstrate this more clearly we consider semiclassical calculations presented in (2) which may be used to calculate x and p variances to determine leading order dependence on n

the quantum level. In (2) Shannon's spatial entropies are calculated semiclassically, but not variances or p Shannon's entropy. We wish to consider both of these.

Semiclassical Treatment of a Particle in a Box with Infinite Potential Walls

In (2) a general semiclassical approach is developed for a system with a potential $V(x)$ and classical turning points. A main equation is:

$$\int_{\text{classical turning points}} p(x) dx = n \cdot 3.14 \quad ((1))$$

$P(x)$ = position probability is defined as $N/p(x)$ where $p(x)$ is the classical momentum at x . In other words, the amount of time a classical particle spends in a fixed dx region is considered to be proportional to $P(x)$.

$$p(x) = \sqrt{2m(E-V(x))} \quad ((2)) \text{ where } E(n) \text{ and the turning points are also functions of } n$$

Differentiating ((1)) with respect to n and noting that $p(x \text{ first turning point}) = p(x \text{ second turning point}) = 0$ yields:

$$3.14(2) = 2m \frac{dE}{dn} \int_{\text{turning points}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2m(E-V(x))}} \quad ((3))$$

((3)) may be linked to $\int P(x) dx = 1 = \int N/p(x)$ yielding:

$$N = 2 \cdot 3.14 \cdot 2m \frac{dE}{dn} \quad ((4)) \text{ as shown in (2).}$$

For a particle in a box with infinite potential walls $p(x) = \pm p$ (quantum ave)

$p(\text{quantum ave})$ is an average over all p values from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$. Classically, however, one only sees one number $p(\text{quantum ave})$ which may be to the right or to the left with the same probability. Thus $p_{\text{ave}} = 0$. One may next try to calculate the p and x variances.

$$\text{Momentum variances} = \int_{\text{turning points}} dx P(x) p^2 = \int dx N/p^2$$

$$= \int dx N p \quad \text{From ((1)) } p = n \cdot 3.14/L \quad (L = \text{the distance between the turning points})$$

$$\text{Momentum variance} = n \cdot 2m \cdot .5 \cdot \frac{dE}{dn} \quad \text{but } E = \frac{1}{2m} n^2 \cdot \frac{3.14^2}{L^2} \text{ so}$$

$$\text{Momentum variance} = n^3 \cdot \frac{3.14^2}{L^3} \text{ and}$$

$$\text{Momentum standard deviation} = \sqrt{2} \cdot n \cdot \frac{3.14}{L} \quad ((5))$$

From (3) an exact quantum calculation yields:

$$\text{Momentum standard deviation} = \hbar (2n-1)^{3/4} / L \quad ((6))$$

Setting $\hbar = 1$ one sees that there ((5)) contains n while ((6)) contains $2n-1$. To resolve this issue the RHS of ((1)) may be replaced with $(2n-1)^{3/4}$ which is the correct value for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls. In other words, $p = 3.14 n / L$ is not the correct result, but simply changing n to $(2n-1)$ fixes the problem. For the x variance n dependence disappears to first order (as will be shown) so it does not matter if one uses n or $2n-1$. Thus there is a high n quantum standard deviation for p even though classically the particle is moving with a constant p (although the sign changes) and for each little dt , dx there is no variance from this value.

Similarly the x variance may be calculated in the semiclassical approach:

$$\begin{aligned} X \text{ variance} &= \int_{\text{turning points}} x^2 P(x) dx = \frac{N}{p} \int_{-L/2}^{L/2} x^2 dx \\ &= 2m \frac{dE}{dn} \frac{1}{(2 \cdot 3.14)^2} \left(\frac{1}{p}\right)^{1/3} \left(\frac{1}{4}\right) L^3 = L^2 \cdot \frac{1}{12} \end{aligned}$$

$$X \text{ standard deviation} = L / [\sqrt{3}] \quad ((7))$$

From (3) and exact quantum calculation yields:

$$X \text{ standard deviation} = L / [2 \sqrt{3}] \sqrt{1 - 6 / (n \cdot 3.14)^2} \quad ((8))$$

To first order this is: $L / [2 \sqrt{3}]$ so ((7)) and ((8)) are the same.

Thus the semiclassical approach of (2) yields the exact quantum results of (3).

The Question of $S_p = - \int dp P(p) \ln[P(p)]$

In (2) the semiclassical approach discussed above is used to find the leading order value of $S_x = - \int dx P(x) \ln[P(x)]$. This is applied to a particle in a box with infinite potential walls, an oscillator and some other examples. There is, however, also an $S_p = - \int dp P(p) \ln[P(p)]$ which is not calculated. S_p is important in entropic uncertainty relationships which use $S_x + S_p$.

In (4) entropic uncertainty relationships are calculated for an oscillator which means that S_x and S_p are obtained. The correspondence principle is used to obtain an estimate of S_x i.e.

$$S_x \text{ approximately equal to } - \int dx C/v(x) \ln[C/v(x)] \quad ((9))$$

Where C is a normalization constant and $v(x)$ is the classical velocity. How is S_p estimated in (4)? The oscillator has a special property that the spatial and momentum wavefunctions are of a very similar form namely:

$\exp(-.5axx)H_n(\sqrt{a}x)$ and $\exp(-.5pp/a)H_n(p/\sqrt{a})$ where H_n is a Hermite polynomial ((10))

Thus $S_p = B + \ln(b_1)$ and $S_x = B - \ln(b_1)$ where $b_1 = \sqrt{\hbar w m}$. If one adds then:

$S_p + S_x = 2B$ where $B = -CC \int dy \exp(-yy) H_n(y)H_n(y)$

In other words, knowledge of S_x automatically yields information about S_p so one does not need an extra theoretical approach to obtain S_p .

In general, however, this is not the case. There does seem to be a close link between $W(x)W(x)=P(x)$ and the classical $C/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is velocity. A quantum bound state often has humps for $P(x)$. If these are very sharp and close together as is the case for high n (quantum mlevel) and if there is bad resolution, then $P(x)$ is like the envelope touching these humps. $P(x)$ is an experimental measurable and so if there is a link with classical mechanics there must be a corresponding physical density in this theory. It is argued that this is $dt = dx(\text{constant})/v(x)$. Thus the two are linked.

What is the situation for $a(p)a(p) = P(p)$? It seems that this is different. Consider a particle in a box with infinite potential walls. For the ground state the particle must be contained within $-L/2$ and $L/2$ i.e. the wavefunction is 0 outside of these values. How does that happen? All values of p must contribute to $\text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ so that interference may yield:

$W(x)=0$ outside of $L/2$ and $-L/2$ and $W(x) = C \cos(p(\text{quantum ave}) x)$ within $(-L/2, L/2)$

Where C is a normalization constant and $\cos(p L/2) = 0$ so $p = 3.14/L$ for $n=1$.

For higher n levels, one still requires that $W(x)$ is 0 outside $-L/2$ and $L/2$. This holds even for very high n , so there is still a range of p values involved even though within $(-L/2, L/2)$ one has many closely spaced sinusoidal peaks giving the semblance of classical motion if one takes the envelope i.e. has bad resolution. Even the variance of p then follows from a semiclassical approach as shown above. Thus interference may still exist at very high n even though the envelope of $P(x)$ appears to be classical.

$S_p = - \int P(p) \ln(P(p))$, however, still seems to remain quantum mechanical. As a result, it does not seem that one may use a semiclassical approach to calculate it (except in the oscillator case where it is very close in value to S_x which may be approximated semiclassically.) In (5) S_p is calculated for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls. It is dependent on n , but approaches a constant involving the Euler constant. This value does not seem to be readily obtainable from a semiclassical approach. This is important because it would mean that the correspondence principle only holds in a spatial sense, not in terms of momentum entropy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we show that the semiclassical approach of (2) may be used to calculate the x and p variances of a particle in a box with infinite potential walls. To do this, however, one needs to have a sense of why a statistical scenario still holds for large n when classical mechanics is

deterministic. We argue that if one has an ensemble of particles in boxes with infinite potential walls and does not have information linking x and t , then the picture is still statistical. This should also hold for classical boxes. In such a case the average momentum is 0 and there is a variance of p . In other words, the classical ensemble becomes statistical because one has lost information linking x and t in each box. We argue that the large n quantum case mimics this scenario.

We also argue, however, that $S_p = - \int dp P(p) \ln(P(p))$ may be a quantum quantity which does not lend itself to a semiclassical approximation. For the oscillator S_x and S_p are very similar and S_x may be calculated semi-classically. In fact all S_x may be estimated semi-classically for high n . For a particle in a box with infinite potential walls, however, it seems that a semiclassical approach does not exist. Furthermore whether $n=1$ or n is very high one needs the full range of $\exp(ipx)$'s to ensure that interference eliminates the wavefunction outside of the box. Thus S_p seems to be a quantum type of value even though it loses its n dependence and approaches a constant as n becomes very large. This constant, however, involves the Euler constant and so it is possible that it is not easily obtained via some kind of semiclassical approach. If this is the case, S_p is an indication that although there may be a spatial correspondence principle, there may not be a momentum one at least with respect to momentum entropy because momentum variance may be calculated semi-classically as shown above.

References

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